

Correlation between intra-abdominal pressure and lung mechanics during laparoscopic gynecology

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Abstract: Surgical data science has introduced practical solutions to overcome the complexity of the surgical workflow inside the operating room by developing systems that capture available data from medical devices, analyze them, and provide predictive models. Understanding the impacts of surgical activities performed by the surgeon and the physiological reactions of the patient plays a key role to develop such smart systems. In this paper, the impact of insufflating the abdominal cavity with CO₂ during the laparoscopic procedures on the lung mechanics were studied. Results show high correlation between intra-abdominal pressure, airway peak pressure, and lung compliance.

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I. Introduction

With increasing demands to improve patient treatment, operating rooms (ORs) have witnessed rapid development of technologies and surgical devices for performing and monitoring the surgical procedures. Moreover, future ORs will incorporate knowledge-based analysis and data fusion from all utilized medical devices for different medical disciplines [1]. The main purpose is to optimize surgical treatment by analyzing all available data and promote better collaboration between the surgical team and the anesthesiologist.

Many approaches have been introduced to optimize surgical workflow, for instance by detecting surgical phases [1, 2]. However, the correlation between surgical actions and physiological reactions has not been intensively investigated yet. In fact, understanding the effects of surgical activities on the vital parameters of patients during surgical procedures enables identifying any possible hazards and developing preemptive approaches to reduce the risk.

The effect of intra-abdominal pressure during laparoscopic procedures on the respiratory system have been investigated during the last years [3], and in this work, the correlation between intra-abdominal pressure (IAP) and lung mechanics was addressed.

II. Material and methods

The data used in this study consist of real time recordings of two laparoscopic gynecology procedures from the surgical devices, mainly the Insufflator device, the anesthesia machine and the patient monitor. The data were recorded at the Schwarzwald-Baar clinic in Villingen-

Schwenningen, Germany. For exhaustive details on the recording procedure, such as the architecture of the data recording system, software, or protocols please refer to Abdulbaki Alshirbaji et al. [4]. Raw data were pre-evaluated to check any incorrect recordings and to correct skews in timestamps received from the devices.

Table 1: Ventilation settings during the surgical procedure, and the target intra-abdominal pressure (IAP). The fourth column shows the changes of the breathing frequency during the procedure. IMV is the abbreviation of Intermittent mandatory ventilation

Subject	Ventilation mode	Tidal volume [mL]	Breathing frequency	Target IAP [mmHg]
S1	IMV	440	10 12 10 12	14
S2	IMV	380	10 9 10 12 14 11	14

II.1. Data processing

The correlation was estimated between IAP and both the airway peak pressure and the dynamic lung compliance that is defined as:

$$C_{dyn} = \frac{V_{T,exp}}{P_{peak} - PEEP} \quad (1)$$

Where C_{dyn} is the dynamic lung compliance; $V_{T,exp}$ is the expiratory tidal volume, P_{peak} is the airway peak pressure, $PEEP$ is Positive end-expiratory pressure.

The intra-abdominal pressure signal was filtered to remove high frequencies and thus ensure consistency between the different data springs.

Figure 1: Correlation between intra-abdominal pressure and airway peak pressure and dynamic lung compliance for two patients undergoing laparoscopic gynecology surgeries. a and b show the correlation for the first subject, while c and d show the correlation for the second subject. Zero values of intra-abdominal pressures represent the surgical phases before insufflating the abdomen and after deflating the abdomen. Pearson coefficients and R^2 s are presented on each figure.

III. Results and discussion

The changes in airway peak pressures and lung compliance were highly correlated to the applied intra-abdominal pressure during the surgical procedure. When the IAP increases the airway peak pressure increases (Fig. 1a,1c), and the lung compliance decreases (Fig. 1b,1d).

To estimate the correlation between both signals, the Pearson coefficient and R^2 were calculated (see Fig.1). The R^2 for the first subject was 0.90, but the R^2 for the second subject was much lower at 0.75. This can be explained when considering changes of ventilation settings (PEEP, breathing frequency, or Inspiration/Expiration ratio) undertaken by the anesthesiologist, which affected the airway pressure. Indeed, during the second procedure the breathing frequency had been changed several times (see Table 1). Hence, a model that incorporates breathing frequency should be considered to get an accurate correlation between the IAP and lung mechanics.

The effects of intra-abdominal pressure on the cardiovascular system are also an important concept that need to be investigated in future work. Moreover, future work should also focus on evaluating the correlation between other physiological parameters and surgical actions, such as electrosurgical cutting and coagulating.

IV. Conclusions

Intra-abdominal pressure increases the airway peak pressure and reduces the lung compliance. Therefore, online monitoring of surgical activities and analyzing physiological reactions to them form the basis to generate predictive models to preemptively inform the anesthesiologist and surgeon about possible complications.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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